

UIUC/NDS at the 2016 bioCADDIE Challenge

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Introduction

The 2016 bioCADDIE Challenge is a TREC-like evaluation competition for the retrieval of metadata describing biomedical datasets. Working in the language modeling framework, our submissions explore document priors and the use of query modeling and expansion using the PubMed Central open-access subset.

Experimental Data

Documents

The bioCADDIE Challenge document collection contains a snapshot of 794,992 metadata documents from 23 repositories included in DataMed. Documents use a common metadata schema, which provides some structure for the heterogenous sources. Record completeness varies across repositories.

Repository	# docs	Proportion
clinicaltrials	192,500	0.2421
bioproject	155,850	0.1960
pdb	113,493	0.1428
geo	105,033	0.1321
dryad	67,455	0.0848
arrayexpress	60,881	0.0766
dataverse	60,303	0.0759
neuromorpho	34,082	0.0429
gemma	2,285	0.0029
proteomexchange	1,716	0.0022

Table 1: Documents counts and collection proportions of top 10 repositories.

Table 1 summarizes the per-repository document counts and collection proportions for the top 10 repositories. The distribution of documents across repositories is non-uniform,

with the top 5 repositories contributing 80% of the test collection.

Queries

Track organizers provided 36 example queries and 15 official test queries for evaluation. These are considered to be queries and not information needs. Query strings are provided without any additional descriptive or narrative information. Below are two complete example queries:

- EA1. Find data of all types related to TGF- β signaling pathway across all databases
- EA5. Search for data of all types on multiple sclerosis of all types across all databases

Relevance judgments are provided in TREC qrel format for 6 of the example queries using three levels of relevance: 0 (not relevant), 1 (relevant), and 2 (highly relevant).

Evaluation

Official submissions are evaluated based on the inferred normalized discounted cumulative gain (infNDCG) metric. Inferred NDCG is considered to be more robust than standard nDCG for incomplete judgements [6].

Experiments

All experiments use the Indri¹ system and the uiucGSLIS `ir-tools` toolkit². For comparison, we index the collection without stemming and Krovetz stemmed, but no stopping in either case. We explored the following:

- *Baseline retrieval models*: We compare several baseline models including Indri TFIDF, Okapi BM25, standard query likelihood [5], relevance models [3], and sequential dependence model [4].
- *Query representations*: We compare the original queries to stopped, stemmed, and manually constructed query representations.
- *Source repository prior*: We explore two approaches to estimating the prior probability of document relevance based on the source repository.
- *Relevance models based on PubMed Central open-access articles*: We compare traditional relevance models based on the metadata documents to models estimated using PMC open-access collection full text.

Baseline retrieval models

For initial exploration, we compare TFIDF, Okapi BM25, query likelihood, relevance model, and sequential dependence model baselines with parameters as described in Table 2.

¹<http://www.lemurproject.org/indri.php>

²<https://github.com/uiucGSLIS/ir-tools>

TFIDF and Okapi BM25 baselines were selected because these are commonly used models in Elasticsearch, the system used by DataMed. For our experiments, Indri implementations of these models were used with default parameters.

Since we work in the language modeling framework, the query likelihood baseline is used for comparison. Due to the noisiness of the official queries for this track, we also included the two-stage smoothing model [7], which performs comparably to TFIDF and BM25 for longer and noisier queries. Relevance modeling is used as a baseline feedback model. Parameters were set empirically based on the training data.

Figure 1 shows the sensitivity of the query likelihood Dirichlet μ parameter as well as relevance model feedback documents (fbDocs), feedback terms (fbTerms), and RM3 mixing (λ) parameters. All values are reported using on the 6 training queries using the inferred NDCG (infNDCG) metric.

Our final baseline, the sequential dependency model (SDM), was selected because of its superior performance for on queries with n-gram terms. The individual weights were again chosen empirically based on the training queries.

From these plots, we see consistently higher performance of the stemmed and manual queries. All query representations are sensitive to low values of μ and λ . Based on this analysis, we selected the parameter values for the QL and RM3 baselines.

Name	Description	Parameters
TFIDF	Indri BM25TF	$k_1 = 1.2, b = 0.75$
BM25	Indri Okapi BM25	$k_1 = 1.2, b = 0.75, k_3 = 7$
QL	Query likelihood	$\mu = 2500$
Two-stage	Two-stage smoothing	$\mu = 2500, \lambda = 0.4$
RM3	Relevance model	$\mu = 2500, docs=10, terms=25, \lambda = 0.75$
SDM	Sequential dependence	$w_1 = 0.75, w_2 = 0.1, w_3 = 0.15$

Table 2: Baseline retrieval models

Query representations

Queries were converted to the Indri format for evaluation (lowercase, punctuation removed). We explored five different query representations:

- **orig**: Unmodified official queries
- **stop**: Stopped using the standard Indri stoplist
- **stem**: Stemmed using the Krovetz stemmer and stopped using the standard Indri stoplist
- **short**: Manually constructed short queries using the procedures described below

For the manually constructed queries (**short**), we removed common text from the queries that seemed unrealistic in real user queries. For example, query EA1 Find data of all types related to TGF- β signaling pathway across all databases is shortened to TGF- β signaling pathway. The query EA5 Search for data of all types on multiple sclerosis of all types across all databases is shortened to simply multiple sclerosis. We suggest that the queries provided by track organizers are in fact information

Figure 1: Sensitivity of (a) Dirichlet mu, (b) RM fbDocs, (c) RM fbTerms, and (d) RM3 lambda for unmodified (orig), stopped, stemmed (krovetz) and manual (short) queries

needs and these manually constructed queries are more representative actual user queries that might be entered into a search box.

Figure 2 compares the performance of the different query representations for each baseline model based on the infNDCG metric. Note, with only six training queries the value of these comparisons is limited. Stopping and stemming improved performance across all models, as did manually shortening the original queries.

Figure 2: Comparison of query representations and retrieval models by infNDCG

Source repository prior

Standard query likelihood scoring assumes a uniform prior on documents. Non-uniform priors have been found to be effective in a number of domains [1, 8, 2].

We expect that some document sources (i.e., repositories) will have a higher probability of producing relevant documents than others to specific queries. Given each source repository S and relevant documents in the training data, we can estimate $p(S)$ based on training data using the Laplace-smoothed maximum likelihood estimate:

$$\hat{p}_{MLE}(S) = \frac{c(S, R) + \epsilon}{|R| + \epsilon|S|}$$

Where S is the document source repository, R is a boolean indicator of relevance, and $\epsilon = 1$.

Another option is to use pseudo-relevance information based on the top N documents returned for a query. This provides an estimate of query-dependent probability of a repository producing a relevant document.

$$\hat{p}_{PR}(S|Q) = \frac{c(S) + \epsilon}{N + \epsilon|S|}$$

The scoring function then becomes:

$$score(Q, D) = p(D|Q) \cdot p(S)$$

PubMed Central expansion models

The `pubmed` queries were constructed using a standard RM3 approach using an index of the PubMed Central Open Access subset for non-commercial use. As with the bioCADDIE documents, indexes were constructed using unstemmed and Krovetz stemmed documents. The RM3 parameters were set empirically based on the training queries. We expect that the expansion terms from the text-rich and topically-relevant PubMed collection will be of a higher quality than terms from the sparser bioCADDIE documents.

Submitted runs

We submitted five runs to the 2016 bioCADDIE Challenge. The first two runs, `uiuc-sdm` and `uiuc-rm3` are baselines intended to diversify the judgement pool. Neither of these methods was included in the list of official baseline models. Run `uiuc-pmc-rm3` is based on our PubMed Central expansion models. Run `uiuc-rm3-prior2` is based on RM3 with repository priors estimated using pseudo-relevance feedback. Queries for all submitted runs were stopped with the Indri stoplist and Krovetz stemmed. Preliminary infNDCG and NDCG scores are provided based on the example queries. NDCG is calculated using `trec_eval`, infNDCG is calculated using `sample_eval.pl` from the TREC Clinical Track³.

Run name	infNDCG	NDCG
<code>uiuc-pubmed</code>	0.2392	0.4714
<code>uiuc-rm3</code>	0.2539	0.4711
<code>uiuc-pubmed-prior2</code>	0.2556	0.4778
<code>uiuc-sdm</code>	0.2613	0.4519
<code>uiuc-rm3-prior2</code>	0.2990	0.4843

Table 3: Preliminary results based on training data

References

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³http://trec.nist.gov/data/clinical/sample_eval.pl

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